

FACTORS AFFECTING THE BALLISTIC IMPACT RESISTANCE OF KEVLAR LAMINATES

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A multiple exposure high speed photographic method has been used to study the interactions between targets and projectiles. Targets examined have included single Kevlar 49 yarns and single and two-ply specimens of Kevlar 49 fabric. The latter were tested without a matrix, in a polyester resin matrix and in a silicone rubber matrix.

A value of 8700 ms^{-1} for the longitudinal strain wave velocity in Kevlar 49 has been calculated using measurements taken from photographs. This value, together with other experimental measurements, has been used to determine the Young's modulus and the fracture strain of Kevlar 49 at ballistic rates. Both have similar values to those measured at conventional rates.

When a standard projectile strikes Kevlar 49 fabric of the type used in these tests, it interacts directly with six yarns. However, the fabric absorbs considerably more energy than the maximum which may be absorbed by six yarns acting independently.

The use of a low strain to fracture polyester resin matrix drastically reduces the penetration velocity of single plies of Kevlar 49 fabric. A high strain to fracture silicone rubber matrix has a similar but much smaller effect.

When two-ply laminates are tested specimens which are matrix-free and those with a silicone rubber matrix behave as if the plies are independent of each other. In specimens with a polyester resin matrix a synergistic effect of the two plies has been observed.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) materials have been developed for helmet and body armour applications. They have superior resistance to dents and higher resistance to penetration by ballistic impact than competitive metallic materials having the same weight per unit area. This has been due to the use of new fibres and fabrics as reinforcement in composite systems.

The mechanisms controlling the resistance of composite systems to penetration or denting during ballistic impact are not clearly understood. Many mathematical models have been suggested [1, 2, 3] to describe the interactions of fibres or fabrics or composites with projectiles travelling at ballistic velocities. Whilst some of these models describe the behaviour of idealised impractical systems very well, none, as far as the present authors are aware, have been developed to describe real systems or to the stage where computer simulation may be used to optimise materials choice, manufacturing procedures and design of the armour for ballistic impact resistance purposes.

Fabrics of glass, carbon and nylon fibres and of cotton and Kevlar yarns have been used in a very wide variety of matrices in empirical development programmes to produce the systems which are currently in use. It is very difficult from considerations of commercial systems to decide which properties of the components of the systems are most important. Within each general type of fibre or yarn, different specific types are used in differing types of weave, with differing surface treatments in differing types of matrix. In addition practical systems are designed to specific maximum weight. This leads to the maximum thickness of any system which may be employed being dependent on its density.

In 1967 Ruggier [4] described work in which the effect of varying the matrix used in glass reinforced systems was examined. A wide range of matrix types including polyesters, epoxies, polyurethanes and vinyls were used. The polyurethanes and polyesters gave the best performance among the systems in which only the matrix type differed. Modifications to polyesters or epoxies by the inclusion of second phase particles as crack stoppers did not seem to affect ballistic resistance but flexibilizing, by reducing the degree of cross linking, did. In the same work it was observed that the better systems delaminated most during impact. It was suggested that the delamination was an energy absorbing mechanism in its own right and that a poor fibre matrix bond strength aided delamination and improved performance. This was not supported however in experiments where the properties of glass polyester systems having many lightweight plies or a smaller number of heavier plies were compared. No difference in performance was measured.

In unpublished work by one of the present authors the properties of Kevlar 49 fabric laminates were examined. Specimens were prepared using a standard fabric with a polyester matrix, a phenolic matrix and no matrix. The number of plies was adjusted to allow a range of areal densities from 6 to 10 kg m⁻² to be examined. Very considerable delamination occurred in the resin bonded specimens but the total energy absorbed seemed to be related to the absolute number of fabric plies used rather than to the type of matrix. This suggests that failure of the resin in delamination is only important in that it enables the individual plies to behave as if no resin were present.

Work using multiple ply specimens has been useful in comparing properties of specific systems but it has not assisted in a determination of the important mechanisms involved. The work described in this paper has examined single Kevlar yarns and single and two-ply Kevlar fabric laminates. The laminates have been made using a low strain to fracture stiff polyester resin matrix, a very high strain to fracture compliant silicone rubber matrix and no matrix at all. Kevlar has been used because it is recognised as one of the most interesting anti-ballistic materials at present.

Standard fragment simulators have been used as impacting projectiles and their kinetic energy before and after impact were measured. The impact events have been

monitored using high speed photography. The work reported is part of a larger programme in which the way that single yarns absorb impact energy is being investigated and the ways in which the energy absorbing mechanisms are changed by weaving into a fabric, by impregnating fabrics with matrices and by increasing the number of plies in matrix free and laminated specimens are being studied.

MATERIALS

Kevlar 49

Kevlar 49 yarn and fabric were used in this work. The yarn was 1420 denier consisting of 1000 continuous filaments. Its modulus was 131 GNm^{-2} and its fracture strain was 2.6%, both measured at conventional rates. The fabric used in these tests was Kevlar 49 fabric, style 328 (U.K. D208) - a plain weave of the 1420 denier yarn with 670 yarns/metre. It was supplied in the scoured condition, that is with the weaving lubricant removed to assist "wetting out" during laminating.

Matrices

Two different matrices have been used. They were chosen for their extreme properties and ease of handling. They were: a high modulus polyester resin (A2785CV) with a strain to fracture of 2% (less than that of Kevlar 49) and a low modulus silicone rubber (RTV602) with a strain to fracture of 200%. Both single and two-ply laminates were manufactured and tested.

BALLISTIC TEST PROCEDURES

Ballistic tests were carried out on single yarns and on fabric specimens both with and without a matrix. For each type of specimen a range of projectile velocities which encompassed the penetration velocity was used. The projectiles were cylinders of silver steel with one end chamfered as shown in Fig. 1. The incident and residual velocities of the projectile were measured using an electrical method. From these values the energy lost by the projectile (or that absorbed by the specimen) could be calculated.

Figure 1 Projectile

Figure 2 Layout for Photography

A Single Yarns Direct Lighting

B Fabric Shadow Lighting

When single yarns were tested each end of the yarn was glued to a small aluminium plate. The plates were then clamped securely. There was no appreciable pretension in the yarns. When Kevlar fabric without a matrix was tested pull-out of the yarns was prevented by impregnating the edges of the specimen with polyester resin. This precaution was necessary since if pull-out is allowed to occur a very pointed projection of the fabric and a drop in the energy absorbed by the specimen result. The specimens were clamped at the edges. Two-ply specimens were made by clamping two single-ply specimens together. Laminates were also clamped at the edges but two-ply specimens with a matrix were manufactured as such - they were not two single plies clamped together.

High speed photography was used to monitor the interaction between the specimen and the projectile. The tests were carried out in a dark room and a multiple flash technique was used. A camera viewing the specimen had its shutter open throughout the test. The projectile hit a pair of foils immediately in front of the target making electrical contact between them. The resulting electrical pulse triggered six flashes of light so that they occurred successively during the interaction. Thus six superimposed images were obtained on a single piece of film. The interval between flashes could be varied from 20 μ s to 200 μ s. Fig. 2A shows the experimental layout and Fig. 3 is a photograph of a single yarn under impact taken using this method.

When photographs were taken of fabric specimens under impact the flashes were directed at a white background so that the outline of the moving fabric appeared as a shadow. Fig. 2B shows the experimental layout and Fig. 5 is an example of a photograph taken in this way. This method was used since, if the flashes were pointed directly at the fabric the weave pattern caused confusion in interpretation of the photographs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Single Yarns

The aim of our work on single yarns has been to determine the stress-strain relationship for Kevlar at ballistic loading rates. Fig. 3 is a multiple flash photograph taken of the interaction between a projectile and single yarn. The yarn was supported during the test as described earlier. The interval between the flashes was 25 μ s and six positions of the yarn and the projectile may be seen. Photographs of this type enable the position of the projectile and the total length of the yarn (and therefore the change in length of the yarn) to be measured at a number of times

during the interaction.

The general behaviour of the yarn, as observed in photographs such as Fig. 3 is consistent with the model for transverse impact on yarns proposed by Smith et. al. [1, 5, 6] and investigated by Stewart et. al. [7]. This model suggests that a longitudinal strain front travels from the point of impact along the yarn in both directions. Its velocity, C_0 , is constant and its intensity, ϵ_0 , is dependent on the impact velocity. As the velocity of the projectile decreases during the interaction the value of ϵ_0 decreases. If, however, the impact velocity is considerably higher than that required to break the yarn, then the value of ϵ_0 may be regarded as constant throughout the interaction since the velocity of the projectile does not decrease substantially. The rate of increase in length of the yarn is $2C_0\epsilon_0$ and this increase is accommodated by transverse displacement of the yarn.

Figure 3 Single Yarn Under Impact
 Incident velocity of projectile: 123 ms^{-1}
 Interval between flashes: $25\mu\text{s}$

By considering the rate of change of momentum in the yarn Smith [1] demonstrated that the tensile force in the yarn, T , is given by the expression

$$T = U^2 M (1 + \epsilon) \quad (1)$$

where U is the velocity at which the transverse displacement travels along the yarn, M is the mass per unit length of the yarn and ϵ is the local strain in the yarn close to the impact point, ϵ may be a multiple of ϵ_0 due to reflections of the longitudinal strain front. The value of U may be measured from photographs and M is known, thus if ϵ is determined T may be calculated.

Figure 4 Results of Ballistic Tests on Kevlar Fabric Without a Matrix

Incident velocity of projectile: 166 ms^{-1}

Interval between flashes: 50 μs

Figure 5 Kevlar Fabric Without a Matrix Under Impact (Single-ply)

The increase in length of the yarn is given by $2C_0\epsilon_0 t$ where t is the time from the start of the interaction and this may be measured for a number of values of t from the photographs. The theoretical value for C_0 , the sonic velocity in Kevlar, is 9500 ms^{-1} based on Du Pont data in the expression $C_0 = \sqrt{E/\rho}$ where E is the Youngs modulus and ρ is the density. Direct measurements to confirm this value failed to give consistent results and it was necessary to use an indirect method. The method used depended upon the fact that when the longitudinal strain front travels through the transversely displaced material (after reflection) it gives rise to a discontinuity in this otherwise straight section of material. This is due to the differing levels of strain ahead of and behind the strain front. When the position of the discontinuity (corresponding to the position of the strain front) is determined the distance travelled by the strain front is still uncertain since the number of reflections which have occurred is unknown. However, a number of possible path lengths, based on different numbers of reflections, may be calculated. A value of C_0 based on each of these path lengths may also be calculated. Consideration of all six exposures associated with a particular impact enables the number of possible values of C_0 to be reduced to one or two. A number of photographs of tests at different impact velocities have been analysed in this way. The estimate of C_0 which was common to all was $8700 \pm 100 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ and this has been taken as the real value of C_0 .

Using the value of 8700 ms^{-1} for C_0 the values of ϵ_0 corresponding to a number of impact velocities have been determined from the rate of change of length during impact ($2C_0\dot{\epsilon}_0$). The values of T corresponding to these values of ϵ_0 have also been calculated using Eq. (1). The results show that for strains in the region 0.5% to 1.5% the modulus measured at ballistic rates is the same as that measured at conventional rates. This will be extended to higher strains in further work. At present there is no evidence to suggest that a change in modulus occurs with increasing strain.

The average strain in yarns when fracture occurred was 2.4 to 2.65%. The fracture strain measured at conventional rates is 2.6 to 2.7%. We conclude, therefore, that since the average strain is similar to the fracture strain, the strain energy which may be absorbed by a yarn during ballistic impact is essentially the same as that which may be absorbed under conventional testing conditions.

The penetration velocity for a single yarn in our tests was below 50 ms^{-1} . In tests at impact velocities up to 140 ms^{-1} the values of ϵ_0 lay in the range 0 to 0.15%. Therefore a large number of reflections of the strain front were necessary to cause failure. The energy absorbed by the yarns during impact was always between 80% and 100% of the calculated maximum strain energy for the same length of yarn loaded at conventional rates. The kinetic energy of the yarns at failure was small due to their very low mass. We conclude that the variation in total energy absorbed is due to the variation in the average strain in the yarns when the local strain at the points of support or at the impact point exceeds the fracture strain.

Fabrics

Fig. 4 shows the results of the ballistic tests on Kevlar fabric without a matrix. The energy absorbed by the specimen is plotted as a function of impact velocity. The broken line A represents the maximum strain energy which may be absorbed by six yarns, six being the number of yarns hit directly by the projectile. The line B represents the kinetic energy of the projectile as a function of its velocity and the point where A and B cross represents the minimum penetration velocity for six yarns since at the penetration velocity all the projectile energy is converted to strain energy in the yarns and at the instant of penetration the kinetic energy is zero. The line C represents the sum of the strain energy (Line A) and the kinetic energy of six yarns, assuming that their entire length is moving with the residual velocity of the projectile when maximum strain energy has been transferred to the yarns. Line C therefore represents the maximum energy which may be absorbed by six yarns during impact.

Photographic records show that points X, Y and Z in Fig. 4 relate to tests in which the projectile was tumbling during its flight. This resulted in a corner of

Figure 6 Results of Ballistic Tests on Kevlar Fabric in a Polyester Resin Matrix

Figure 7 Kevlar Fabric in a Polyester Resin Matrix Under Impact (Single-ply)

Incident velocity of projectile: 69 ms^{-1}
Interval between flashes: $25 \mu\text{s}$

the projectile striking the fabric and a penetration in which some yarns were pushed aside rather than strained and broken. However, the important observation on the single ply results is that in the velocity range 120 to 250 ms⁻¹ much more energy may be absorbed than is indicated on line C. It is clear therefore that a significant contribution to energy absorption is made by the fabric as a whole.

In order to take advantage of this effect it is necessary to understand something of the mechanisms of energy transfer from one yarn to another in the fabric.

There are many published works on theoretical analyses of energy absorption in fabrics [2, 3, 8, 9, 10, 11]. They tend, however, to consider highly idealised systems and they are difficult to translate into practical terms.

A simplification of the mechanisms which occur during ballistic impact on fabrics may be presented as follows:

1. A longitudinal strain front and the resulting transverse displacement are developed in the yarns which are directly impacted (primary yarns) as described above for single yarns.
2. The travelling strain front encounters cross-over yarns and at the cross-overs some reflection occurs. This leads to a reduction in the strain intensity in the travelling front and an increase in the strain intensity behind the cross-over. Continuing reflections of this type lead to the development of a negative strain gradient away from the impact point. Clearly as reflection becomes more efficient, the fracture strain at the impact point is reached more quickly and the total energy absorbed before penetration is reduced.
3. Yarn material moving towards the impact point behind the strain front is constrained by friction against the cross-over yarns. This has the effect of transversely displacing the contact point on the cross-over yarn and of sharing the momentum of the primary yarn towards the impact point with the cross-over yarn. The effect of this is to unload the primary yarn. High friction between the cross-over yarn and the primary yarn aids this mechanism.
4. When material starts to move transversely, at the advancing transverse displacement front, it does so by converting the momentum towards the impact point along the yarn into momentum parallel to the trajectory of the projectile. The rate of arrival of momentum at the transverse displacement front in a single yarn is given by

$$\frac{d(mv)}{dt} = C_o^2 \epsilon M \quad (2)$$

where M is the mass per unit length of the yarn. When a cross-over yarn is present at the advancing front this force results in transverse displacement of both the cross-over yarn and the primary yarn. Thus the strain energy in the primary yarn is shared with the cross-over yarn and the primary yarn is unloaded.

It is clear that reflections of the strain front (2 above) are undesirable when maximum energy absorption is being sought. In-plane displacement of cross-over yarns (3 above) is a desirable mechanism since it unloads the primary yarn. However, factors which aid 2 also aid 3 and any benefit gained by unloading may be lost by having a steep strain gradient. Unloading by transverse displacement (4 above) is potentially a very effective mechanism. It is limited, however, by the strain gradient in the primary yarn. If the gradient is steep then total extension of the primary yarn is low. Thus the total extent of the transverse displacement of the primary yarns is low and few cross-over yarns are involved. Conversely if the strain gradient is low many cross-over yarns become involved in energy absorption. The nature of the cross-over appears therefore to be crucial to the energy absorbing performance.

Figure 8 Results of Ballistic Tests on Kevlar Fabric in a Silicone Rubber Matrix

Incident velocity of projectile: 129 ms^{-1}

Interval between flashes: $50 \mu\text{s}$

10mm

Figure 9 Kevlar Fabric in a Silicone Rubber Matrix Under Impact (Single-ply)

Fig. 5 is a multiframe photograph taken during interaction of a projectile with a single ply of fabric. It is clear that a large volume of material is strained and is participating in the energy absorption. Measurements show that the average strain in primary yarns in specimens of this type impacted just above the penetration velocity reached 1.5%. The strain gradient is therefore quite low since the fracture strain is 2.6 - 2.7%. We believe that the reflection coefficient at cross-overs in these specimens is low. This leads to high energy absorption by mechanism 4 above.

The disadvantage of a matrix free fabric is that low energy penetrations such as those represented by points X, Y and Z in Fig. 4 may occur when projectiles are pointed or have sharp corners. It is desirable that the good energy transfer mechanisms of matrix free fabric should be retained but measures should be taken to prevent sideways displacement of yarns by the projectile. One method of accomplishing this is the introduction of a matrix.

Fig. 6 gives results of ballistic tests on Kevlar fabric in a polyester resin matrix. The lines A, B and C are as described for Fig. 4. It is very clear that in this case much less energy is absorbed than the primary yarns alone are capable of absorbing. This indicates either that a very steep strain gradient is developed in the primary yarns or that a completely new penetration mechanism is occurring. The rigid connections provided by the resin at cross-over points should improve reflections of the longitudinal pulse and this should be reinforced by reflections from cracks which occur in the resin. This would lead to the development of a very steep strain gradient in the primary yarn.

Fig. 7 is a multiple flash photograph of an impact on a polyester resin impregnated fabric. No transverse displacement may be detected, therefore very little energy was transferred into the cross-over yarns. Thus it is possible to explain the behaviour of these specimens, qualitatively at least, in terms of the mechanisms listed above. At least six yarns were broken in every test where penetration occurred. The polyester resin was effective in preventing the sideways displacement of yarns but its dramatic effect on fibre cross-overs led to efficient reflection of the strain fronts in the primary yarns, the development of very steep strain gradients and poor energy transfer into the bulk material.

The energy absorbing characteristics of the Kevlar fabrics with a silicone rubber matrix are between those of the specimens with no matrix and those with a polyester matrix as shown in Fig. 8. For impact velocities between 120 and 150 ms⁻¹ the energy absorbed is higher than that which could be absorbed by six independent yarns. The photograph in Fig. 9 shows that a considerable volume of material is transversely displaced. This is similar to the behaviour of matrix free fabric. However, in this case no low velocity penetrations due to the pushing aside of yarns were observed, although it was observed that the silicone rubber did not wet the yarns as the polyester resin did. The average strain in the primary yarns at the instant of penetration in tests close to the penetration velocity never exceeded 1.2%. This is lower than the value measured in fabric without a matrix, indicating that a steeper strain gradient is developed and therefore that reflections at cross-overs are more efficient.

In single ply specimens the silicone rubber has been much more satisfactory than the polyester resin as a matrix. It has prevented the sideways displacement of yarns by the projectile and consequent low energy penetrations which occur with matrix free fabrics. However, it has also caused a decrease in the amount of energy which may be absorbed during impact and in the penetration velocity.

The energy absorbed in fabric specimens with and without matrices is observed to decrease as impact velocity increases above the penetration velocity. This is because the value of ϵ_0 increases with increasing impact velocity. This leads to steeper strain gradients and shorter interaction times since fewer reflections are necessary before failure.

Figs. 4, 6 and 8 also give data for impacts on two-ply specimens. The lines for energy absorption above the penetration velocity have been drawn as the best fit to a limited number of points. The important observation from these results is that

for the matrix free specimens and for those with a silicone rubber matrix the behaviour of a two-ply specimen is equivalent to that of two independent plies. Thus if a projectile were to strike a two-ply matrix free specimen at 260 ms^{-1} it would penetrate with a residual velocity of 150 ms^{-1} . If a projectile with the same velocity were to strike a single ply it would penetrate with a residual velocity of 218 ms^{-1} . If it were then to strike a second single ply it would penetrate and the residual velocity would be 150 ms^{-1} . This relationship holds for all velocities on Figs. 4 and 8.

In the case of the fabric with a polyester matrix, a two-ply specimen is a much more effective energy absorber than two single plies. A projectile striking a single ply at 100 ms^{-1} would penetrate with a residual velocity of 88 ms^{-1} . If it were then to strike a second single ply it would penetrate with a residual velocity of 72 ms^{-1} . A similar projectile striking a two-ply specimen would be stopped. This effect has not been explained but some delamination occurred in two-ply specimens and it is possible that this contributed to the synergistic effects obtained by using two plies. In other work we have observed that when 30 plies of resin free material were tested they had the same penetration velocity as a 30 ply laminate with a polyester resin matrix. Considerable delamination also occurred in this case. This observation points to the possibility that a laminate with a polyester resin matrix may, at more than a critical number of plies, be superior in stopping power to a matrix-free specimen or to one with a silicone rubber matrix having the same number of plies.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The Youngs modulus and the fracture strain of Kevlar 49 yarns measured at ballistic rates are the same as those measured at conventional rates.
2. The velocity of the longitudinal strain front in Kevlar 49 yarns is 8700 ms^{-1} .
3. In Kevlar 49 fabric the nature of the yarn cross-over connections is critical in determining the ballistic energy absorbing capability.
4. In Kevlar 49 fabric energy is transferred from the primary yarns to the cross-over yarns by the transverse motion of the primary yarns rather than by dispersion of the longitudinal strain pulse.
5. The effect of a polyester resin matrix on the behaviour of Kevlar fabric is to enhance the reflection of the strain front at yarn cross-overs. This increases the strain gradient in the primary yarns and decreases the energy absorbing capability of the fabric.
6. The silicone rubber matrix used in this work does not wet Kevlar 49 but it does prevent it being displaced sideways by a penetrating projectile. It enhances the reflection of the strain front and reduces the total energy absorbed. The reduction in energy absorption is much less than that caused by a polyester resin matrix.
7. In ballistic tests on two-ply laminates specimens which are matrix-free and those with a silicone rubber matrix behave as two separate and independent plies. Two-ply laminates with a polyester resin matrix absorb more energy than two isolated single plies would absorb.

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